

APPENDIX

Figure S2: Distribution of the τ_{ik} probability of a postcode i to be in a group k

Figure S3: Estimated mean ($\hat{\mu}_{kj}$, panel A) and variance ($\hat{\sigma}_{kj}^2$, panel B) of substance quantities purchased in a group as a function of the probability of a substance j to be in a group $\hat{\gamma}_{kj}$

Figure S4: Differences and similarities in the clustering of postcodes produced by the mixture model with only 2017 substance purchase data (a) or 2015- 2018 data (b). Postcode within a group share the same colour. Panel c shows proximity of the 2017 groups with 2015-2018 groups on a heatmap, expressed as the percentage of postcodes from 2017 groups that were found in the various 2015-2018 groups. The graph should be read vertically: for example, 2017 group r is split mostly into 2015-2018 groups 21(38%) and 23 (37%), with a small fraction of postcodes also found in 2015-2018 groups 1 (12%) and 13 (10%). In contrast, virtually all postcodes of 2017 group f are found in 2015-2018 group 18.

Figure S5: Variance in probabilities of substances to be in a group as a function of their mean probability to be in a group. Colours indicate core (orange), discriminant (blue) and other (green) substances.

Figure S8: Heatmap of probability y_{kj} , that substance j is used in postcode k . Groups were obtained from a mixture models optimised by maximum likelihood with an iterative method: Expectation Maximisation. Groups were ordered by similar composition of substance purchases. Substances belong to four categories: herbicides, fungicides, insecticides and other targets. Within each category of substances, substances were ordered in increasing number of groups in which they were used. Column A corresponds to the mean probability of use and column B corresponds to the scaled (0,1) variance in probability of use across groups. Asterisks (*) highlight core substances.

Table S1: Complete list of substance's targets name associated with the "other" category

Substance's targets	Number of substances
Acaricide	5
Algicide	1
Attractant	2
Bactericide	1
Nematicide	1
Plant activator	1
Plant growth regulator	11
Rodenticide	2
Safener	1

Table S2 : Correspondence table between crop categories from the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) and aggregated crop categories used in our analyses

CATEGORY FROM RPG	CATEGORY USED
Common wheat	Cereals
Barley	Cereals
Other cereals	Cereals
Miscellaneous	Miscellaneous
Arboriculture	Orchard
Olive tree	Orchard
Fruit Orchard	Orchard
Legumes/Flowers	Legumes/Flowers
Maize	Maize
Nut	Nut
Other oil crops	Other oil crops
Protein crop	Protein crop
Rapeseed oil	Rapeseed oil
Sunflower	Sunflower
Grapevine	Grapevine